

THE STUDY OF THE IMPACT OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES ON STUDENTS' THINKING AS A PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEM

Z.Kh. Abdinazarova

Associate Professor, Department of "Pedagogy, Psychology, and Primary Education,"
Tashkent Institute of Economics and Pedagogy

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***Abstract.** The article examines the influence of pedagogical technologies on students' thinking as a psychological problem, as well as psychologically contradictory aspects of traditional education.*

***Keywords:** pedagogical technology, problem-based learning, motivation, content of education, psychological problem, knowledge, skills, traditional education.*

The educational process can be briefly defined as a specific management process in which a targeted influence is exerted on the pedagogical system. In a certain sense, it can be noted that in the educational process, knowledge is structured and transmitted to others. To ensure the successful implementation of this process, special educational models are applied in the field of pedagogy. These models help organize the rational management of pedagogical systems. The structure and essence of pedagogical models include different types of teaching methods.

In pedagogy, education is mainly divided into three types: the traditional teaching method, the innovative teaching method based on pedagogical technologies, and the programmed teaching method. Below, we will briefly describe their essence.

It should be emphasized that none of the teaching methods mentioned above can be considered a perfect universal approach. Each of them has both positive and negative aspects. However, there are proponents of certain methods who advocate for the exclusive use of their preferred didactic approach. These researchers absolutize the teaching method they consider ideal and tend to overlook its shortcomings. Experience shows that significant achievements in education can be attained only when these methods are optimally integrated.

The first and oldest teaching method is the "**traditional teaching method.**" In this approach, classroom instruction follows a lecture format, where one person speaks while others listen. The distinct feature of traditional teaching is that it allows for the rapid transmission of a large amount of information in a short period. However, its main drawback is that it primarily targets students' memory rather than their thinking abilities. In this method, students' positive qualities, independent thinking, and active engagement develop at a slower pace.

A.A. Verbitsky identifies the psychological contradictions of traditional education as follows:

1. **The first psychological contradiction** – The content of learning (and, consequently, that of the educator) is based on past experiences reflected in a system of symbols, while the subject of learning is oriented toward the future in terms of professional and practical activities. Education that relies on past knowledge and experiences may seem abstract to learners in terms of its future applicability. It is well known that receiving ready-made

knowledge deprives students of opportunities to confront the unknown. Thus, in traditional education, there are no situations that stimulate cognitive development or create problem-solving challenges.

2. **The second psychological contradiction** – The dual nature of educational information. On one hand, information is a part of culture; on the other hand, it serves as a means of assimilating that culture. To resolve this psychological contradiction, educators must connect the abstract nature of educational content with real-life conditions.
3. The next psychological contradiction lies between the integrity of culture and the process of assimilating it through various academic disciplines. This tradition is characterized by the multitude of school teachers and university departments, each specializing in different fields. As a result, instead of forming a holistic perception of reality or the subject being studied, the student acquires a "fragmented mirror" of knowledge. The student is deprived of the opportunity to reconstruct a unified image from these fragmented pieces.
4. Another psychological contradiction is the dynamic nature of culture as a process versus its transmission through static educational systems. In education, pre-prepared learning materials are provided, lacking the developmental dynamics of culture and disconnected from the student's independent life and needs. Consequently, both the learner and culture itself fail to develop.
5. The next psychological contradiction arises between the social form of culture's existence and the individual process of its assimilation by the learner. In traditional education, resolving this contradiction is challenging because students do not synthesize the knowledge they acquire as a collaborative product.

If we analyze the issue closely, the result of these psychological contradictions is the failure to cultivate creative individuality in learners. In conclusion, the main drawback of the traditional education system is its inability to foster creative thinking in students.

At this point, A.A. Verbitsky introduces a significant idea in the field of pedagogical psychology. He argues that traditional teaching methods lead students to engage only in subject-based individual activities, which is not how it should be. To ensure comprehensive education and the development of creative thinking, students must actively participate in learning activities. A similar idea was expressed by I.E. Unt in the 1990s. According to him, in the interaction between the teacher and the student, learning should not be limited to subject-based actions; rather, students must be engaged in meaningful learning activities.

At this point, it is essential to understand the nature of action. Referring to a psychological dictionary, work is described as an activity that possesses both subject-related and socio-cultural structures. It internalizes another person's thoughts and adjusts one's behavior accordingly, following social and moral norms.

Such an interaction between the teacher and the learner necessitates adherence to ethical principles, mutual consideration of their positions, interests, and values. Only under these conditions can we speak of genuine education and acknowledge the inseparable connection between education and upbringing. Whatever a person does, no matter what kind of subject-related action they perform, they always become part of the "fabric" of culture and social relations, thus engaging in meaningful work.

Another major drawback of the traditional education system is its disregard for the personal and life experiences of learners. In such a system, the teacher's instructional materials remain

disconnected from the learner's personal experiences. As a result, knowledge exists merely for the sake of knowledge, and if students cannot relate their personal experiences to the learning material, their creative thinking will not develop. Consequently, the process of nurturing individuals essential to society weakens.

Thus, we have analyzed the psychological and pedagogical impact of traditional education on learners and the psychological contradictions it creates. The primary shortcoming of traditional education is its failure to develop students' creative thinking. Therefore, an alternative teaching approach that, at the very least, shifts learners from passive listeners to active participants is necessary. This demand has led many scholars to research pedagogical methodologies (technologies) that can elevate the education system to a more effective level and accelerate students' intellectual development.

Pedagogical technologies distinguish themselves from traditional education by eliminating its shortcomings, transforming learners into active participants, and creating opportunities for cognitive growth. V.P. Bospalko defines pedagogical technology as "the continuous implementation of a pre-planned educational and training process in practice."

The key difference between pedagogical technologies and other teaching methods is their ability to engage students actively and stimulate their motivation and interest in learning. They include accelerated learning techniques, group learning methods, educational games, and more. Today, the scope of pedagogical technologies has expanded beyond education to various fields. For example, corporate training sessions in production enterprises utilize these technologies, and business games help develop employees' specific skills and competencies. Moreover, in the medical field, certain psychological training methods are being applied to treat mental disorders.

At this point, it is important to highlight that pedagogical and psychological technologies serve three main functions:

1. **Instrumental Function** – This function helps develop specific skills and competencies in learners.
2. **Gnostic Function** – This function focuses on the formation of knowledge and the development of students' thinking abilities.
3. **Socio-Psychological Function** – This function fosters certain socio-psychological skills in students, such as communication skills.

Each function corresponds to specific technologies: game exercises - for the instrumental function, didactic technologies - for the gnostic function, and role-playing games - for the socio-psychological function.

We have briefly analyzed pedagogical technologies above. Now, let us examine the historical origins of pedagogical technologies.

Before discussing the emergence of pedagogical technologies, it is crucial to emphasize their direct connection to problem-based learning. Problem-based learning arose as an educational necessity due to the societal demand for fostering human thinking.

It is also worth noting that the types of education we have reviewed above can be conditionally divided into three categories. However, in practice, these categories function in collaboration with one another.

In summary, we have briefly explored the emergence of pedagogical technologies, their impact on human cognition, and the study of these issues in pedagogical psychology. Additionally,

we have attempted to highlight the role of problem-based learning in the development of pedagogical technologies.

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